

**Guidelines for Assessment and Instruction in
Statistics Education
College Report**

June 2026 Draft

Guidelines for Assessment and Instruction in Statistics Education

College Report

Much has changed since the ASA endorsed the Guidelines for Assessment and Instruction in Statistics Education College Report (hereafter called the GAISE College Report) in 2005.” This sentence served as an introduction to the 2016 revised GAISE College Report and served as motivation for undertaking the current revision process. The current revision (2025) will be made available in stages.

Navigate This Report

- **Executive Summary:** Overview of the revision
- **Recommendations:** Ten comprehensive recommendations for Introductory Statistics and Introductory Data Science
- **Introductory Statistics:** Guidance for Introductory Statistics Courses
- **Introductory Data Science:** Guidance for Introductory Data Science Courses
- **Assessment:** Guidance for evaluating student learning

Previous Versions

Links to previous College GAISE reports: - [2016 GAISE College Report](#) - [2005 Original GAISE College Report](#)

Executive Summary

Executive Summary: GAISE College Report 2025

Key Changes from Previous Versions

The 2025 revision of the GAISE College Report reflects significant evolution in statistics and data science education since the 2016 version. This update reflects that students live, work, and play in a world that is increasingly data-informed and where technology is rapidly evolving.

This is is the first draft of the executive summary and will be updated.

Introductory Statistics Courses

Guidelines for Introductory Statistics Courses

Introductory statistics courses serve as students' first formal encounter with statistical thinking and methodology. These courses should emphasize the statistical process while building conceptual understanding that prepares students for advanced study or informed citizenship.

Student Learning Outcomes for Introductory Statistics

What are Student Learning Outcomes?

Student learning outcomes (SLOs) describe the knowledge, skills, and abilities students should acquire over a given time period. Aside from articulating the specific academic goals for students, they also indicate how students will demonstrate evidence of their learning; that is, SLOs need to be measurable.

Student learning outcomes have different levels of granularity. A program may provide SLOs at the program level, while individual instructors may provide SLOs for their course or even for each individual class meeting. The learning outcomes provided here are at the course level; that is, the SLOs articulate what students should know and be able to do after completing an introductory statistics course.

Our goal was to present a set of SLOs that describe important outcomes for students completing an introductory statistics class. While instructors could use them verbatim, they could also be adapted to meet the specific needs of their students. We expect that most instructors will add, modify, or substitute these SLOs to suit their course.

Why are Course Student Learning Outcomes Important?

SLOs serve multiple purposes. First, they can provide students with a roadmap for what they can expect to know and do after finishing their introductory statistics course. Second, SLOs can help statistics instructors prioritize content, create appropriate assessments, and design instructional materials for their course.

Metaphorically, the SLOs identify the learning destination for the road trip of introductory statistics. The route and itinerary of the course can be mapped out to help students incrementally develop the knowledge, skills, and abilities addressed in the SLOs so that the journey is successful. As such, the use of SLOs can evoke critical, evidence-based thought about student learning.

Student Learning Outcomes vs. The College GAISE Recommendations

The SLOs for introductory statistics provided here serve a very different purpose than the College GAISE Recommendations provided elsewhere in this document. The SLOs for introductory statistics provided here are focused on the outcomes and goals for students' learning (i.e., student-facing), whereas the College GAISE Recommendations are designed to aid instructors and other stakeholders in understanding current best practices in the teaching of statistics and data science (instructor-facing). To continue our road trip metaphor, the College GAISE Recommendations are a general guidebook for road trips. They offer instructional insight and guidance for the trip that is useful for all road trips regardless of the learning destination or route taken.

After completing an Introductory Statistics course, students should be able to:

1. Identify cases, variables, and types of variables in data sets, including multivariable data sets.
2. Explain how study design affects what conclusions can be drawn from the data. In particular, explain the importance of random sampling and random assignment.
3. Identify and interpret appropriate graphs and summary statistics in both univariate and multivariate settings.
4. Use statistical software or apps to create visualizations, produce summary statistics, and carry out the computational aspects of statistical analysis.
5. Articulate the role that random variation plays in statistical inference. In particular, articulate its role in generalizing from a sample to a population.
6. Identify the key methods to use in statistical inference and interpret results from those methods.

7. Recognize that sampling variation is one reason that conclusions drawn from statistical inference might be incorrect, and that replication and reproducibility are important to verify conclusions.
8. Use statistical models, such as linear regression, for prediction.
9. Recognize ethical issues and dilemmas in statistical practice.
10. Communicate, clearly and in context, results obtained from data.

Introductory Data Science Courses

Guidelines for Introductory Data Science Courses

Introductory data science courses introduce students to the interdisciplinary field that combines statistics, computer science, and domain expertise to extract insights from data. These courses should emphasize the data science pipeline while building computational and statistical thinking skills.

This section is under development.

Recommendations for Introductory Statistics and Introductory Data Science

Recommendations for Statistics and Data Science

1. **Teach statistics and data science as processes of gleaning insights from data to inform evidence-based decisions.**

Data summarize the world—indeed, the universe—around us. Data therefore encapsulate information that is essential for understanding what surrounds us and for making decisions. Statistics and data science are, collectively, the science of extracting meaningful information from data to produce insights and analyses. Students learning this science in introductory statistics and data science courses should engage in the *process of working with data*.

Working with data involves studying the context in which data occur, interrogating and summarizing data, formulating research questions that can be answered with data, using appropriate methodology to analyze data, and effectively communicating results involving data. These steps need not proceed in this order, and analyses or summaries may suggest new questions; statistics and data science, like science itself, are often iterative.

For more information and resources, [click here](#).

2. **Emphasize effective written and oral communication of results from data, with attention to the scope and limitations of conclusions.**

Producing results is only one step in learning from data; students must also communicate their findings clearly and accurately, both orally and in writing. This requires responsiveness to both the genre of communication (i.e., oral or written presentation, journal article, newsletter, conversation with classmates, op-ed, etc.) and the audience background.

Effective communication starts with understanding and conveying the provenance of the data—their source, completeness, validity, relevance, and currency—emphasizing their effect on conclusions. Inferences, visualizations, and analyses should be presented as evidence, not definitive proof, of conclusion. Conclusions drawn from data can yield

a better understanding, and [iterations of the process](#) can continue to improve that understanding.

[Ethical communication](#) requires transparently acknowledging limitations and contextualizing results at an audience-appropriate technical level—[keeping the focus on conceptual understanding](#).

For more information and resources, [click here](#).

3. Focus on conceptual understanding rather than algebraic manipulation and formulas.

Given limited instructional time, it is essential to prioritize ideas that promote conceptual understanding over procedural skills. Understanding how and why statistics works is more valuable than the ability to perform manual calculations.

This shift in focus changes how we present topics and assess student learning. Manually calculating statistics like standard deviation or correlation coefficient has little pedagogical value; trained statisticians rely on technology, and so should students. While some basic computation is necessary, complex formulas and distribution tables should be de-emphasized or eliminated. Instead, instructors should introduce only formulas that support deeper conceptual understanding and use technology to automate calculations. Dynamic tools like applets can illustrate statistical concepts effectively, such as how sample size affects standard error, without requiring students to memorize formulas.

Procedural knowledge still has a place—but only when it supports conceptual learning. For example, identifying variable types, exploring relationships, and interpreting results in context reinforce the statistical process better than memorizing formulas. Asking students to manually calculate test statistics and look up p-values may shift focus away from understanding the question and context.

A conceptually strong foundation helps students make sense of statistics in the real world and prepares them for more advanced study. While technical steps matter less in an introductory course, strong conceptual grounding often leads to procedural fluency over time.

For more information and resources, [click here](#).

4. Integrate real data with a context and purpose throughout the course. Select data that are meaningful and engaging to the students.

Real data comes from genuine, practical situations and reflects the complexity of data encountered in everyday life. Integrating real data into a statistics course bridges abstract concepts and real-world applications, making learning more engaging and relevant.

Using data related to topics students care about—like health, sports, or social issues—helps students ask meaningful questions while building statistical skills. Real data supports authentic problem-solving and critical thinking by providing context, such as

its origin and purpose, and exposing students to varied variable types and data sources (e.g., surveys, experiments, business metrics).

Working with real data supports both curricular and pedagogical goals. It emphasizes inquiry over rote learning and exposes students to real-world challenges like missing values or non-standard distributions. *Realistic data*—simulated datasets designed to mimic patterns and challenges of authentic data—can provide controlled yet realistic learning experiences in some situations. Instructors should choose real or realistic data carefully to align with students’ learning needs and instructional goals.

Some potential sources of real datasets include textbooks, online repositories, classroom-generated activities, and collaborations with colleagues in other disciplines. Educational data portals also offer valuable, curated resources.

Real data might include:

- **Authenticity:** Collected for actual research or decision-making purposes.
- **Relevance:** Tied to topics meaningful and engaging to students.
- **Complexity:** Includes real-world features like outliers or missing data.
- **Context:** Comes with background information to support interpretation and application.

For more information and resources, [click here](#).

5. Encourage multivariable thinking.

Multivariable thinking (MVT) is essential for navigating today’s complex, data-rich world. Real-world phenomena are influenced by many factors, and datasets with numerous variables are now common. MVT is no longer just for statisticians—it is a necessary skill for all students to interpret data critically and draw informed conclusions.

MVT has always had a place in statistics education, but students need consistent, structured practice with it. Rather than treating MVT as an add-on, we should integrate it throughout the course—from data exploration to modeling and inference.

Simple ways to begin introducing MVT include encouraging students to consider the broader context of a dataset, having students explore multivariable datasets, using visualizations with three or more variables, and having students brainstorm confounding variables. Additional ideas for introducing MVT in statistics and data science courses are provided in the link below.

For those already including MVT at a beginning level, the link below also includes suggestions for deepening MVT exposure and suggestions for aspirational activities.

For more information and resources, [click here](#).

6. **Incorporate software/apps to explore concepts and work with data.**

Technology should play a central role in statistics and data science courses by reducing the algebraic burden of analysis, enabling the creation of data visualizations, and supporting a deeper understanding of data. Effective tools allow students to shift their focus from manual calculations to interpreting results and grasping key concepts. Technology also provides access to real-world, often large-scale datasets that might otherwise be too complex to explore manually. Additionally, appropriate and vetted use of artificial intelligence (AI) can enhance data understanding and simplify complex calculations.

Using statistical software or applets with capabilities beyond those of graphing calculators is essential in modern statistics and data science courses. While no specific tools are mandated, software and applets that support data wrangling, visualization, numerical summaries, inference, and modeling help instructors focus on interpretation. These technologies also enable students to engage with advanced topics and promote equity by reducing barriers linked to algebraic and computational skills.

For more information and resources, [click here](#).

7. **Emphasize responsible and ethical conduct in the collection and use of data and in their analysis.**

With growing access to real-world datasets and powerful tools, ethics education is more important than ever. Instruction must equip students to responsibly manage data privacy, consent, and transparency in an evolving landscape. Society benefits from informed judgments supported by ethical statistical practice.

Statistical practitioners must commit to making decisions ethically to ensure trustworthy outcomes and protect against harm. The statistical practitioner must understand the provenance of the data—including origins, revisions, and any restrictions on usage—and fitness for use prior to conducting statistical practices. As technology evolves and real-world data becomes more accessible, instruction must address the ethical considerations of data collection, analysis, and communication (Raman et al. 2023).

The **American Statistical Association’s Ethical Guidelines for Statistical Practice (2022)** emphasize transparency, reproducibility, and valid interpretation. Ethical reflection should be woven into each stage of statistical practice, including formulating questions, data collection and preparation, exploratory data analysis (EDA), analysis, communicating results, and adapting to change.

For more information and resources, [click here](#).

8. **Employ evidence-based pedagogies that actively engage students in the learning process.**

Research consistently shows that students learn better when they are actively involved in the learning process rather than passively receiving information (e.g. , Felder and Brent 2024; Lombardi et al. 2021; National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine

2025). Active learning allows students to construct their own understanding, test ideas, and engage in meaningful reflection and dialogue. In statistics and data science, this can be achieved through prediction exercises, real data projects, or the use of manipulatives and technology to explore abstract concepts. Effective instruction centers the student experience, blending brief active strategies with lecture, encouraging both conceptual understanding and deeper engagement. Even small changes—such as think-pair-share, interactive polling, or group reflections—can make a significant difference in learning outcomes.

Successful active learning also requires thoughtful facilitation. Instructors should tailor activities to student backgrounds, build in flexibility for different comfort levels, and foster respectful peer interactions. Incorporating collaborative work, offering students choices in assignments or data sets, and creating space for uncertainty and exploration help students take ownership of their learning. Online courses, too, can support active engagement through tools like discussion boards, video responses, and collaborative tasks. With intentional design and student-centered practices, active learning can enrich statistics and data science education across formats and student populations.

For more information and resources, [click here](#).

9. Use a variety of formative and summative assessments to improve teaching and learning.

Effective teachers use assessment to guide instruction, motivate students, provide feedback, and evaluate performance. Assessments are generally categorized as formative (to support learning) or summative (to evaluate learning). Because the purposes differ, the approach to administration and feedback should also differ. Formative assessments provide ongoing, actionable feedback that helps students adjust their understanding and instructors refine instruction. Summative assessments, on the other hand, are used for evaluation and grading.

Formative assessment should occur during key points in the learning process and provide timely, specific, and non-evaluative feedback. It can take many forms—written comments, class discussions, clicker questions, or think-pair-share activities. These strategies not only support student understanding but also offer instructors insight into where students may be struggling, such as with interpreting p-values. By responding to these insights, instructors can adjust instruction in real time, improving outcomes. Using varied formative strategies also increases student engagement and helps foster a sense of belonging.

For more information and resources, [click here](#).

10. Implement inclusive strategies that create learning environments where all students are valued.

All students deserve the opportunity to succeed in statistics and data science and be prepared for the challenges of our technological society (National Academies of Sciences,

Engineering, and Medicine 2025). Creating these opportunities is both a moral and professional obligation(Charles A. Dana Center 2021).

However, many students face barriers that limit their ability to succeed. Inclusive pedagogy can help address these inequities by fostering equal opportunity and a stronger sense of inclusivity (Byra 2006; Moriña 2022). A supportive classroom community influences how students see themselves in the field and affects their academic and career choices (Valdez and Kelp 2023).

Instructors can start promoting inclusivity during course design by considering accessibility needs and anticipating barriers—for example, students with disabilities, with limited internet access, or who are hesitant to speak in class. These efforts should extend throughout all interactions with students. Our [table of practices](#) provides actionable strategies to help dismantle systemic barriers(National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine 2025).

Collecting student feedback early in the course is vital. Clearly communicating course design intentions and inviting feedback shows students their experiences are valued (Dalzell et al. 2025).

Beyond our resources, numerous tools online can support inclusive teaching across all types of courses. Even small steps toward valuing all learners contribute to a more inclusive and statistically literate society.

For more information and resources, [click here](#).

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Charles A. Dana Center. 2021. “Data Science Course Framework.” URL: [https://www.utdanacenter.org/sites/default/files/2021-05/Data Science Course Framework](https://www.utdanacenter.org/sites/default/files/2021-05/Data_Science_Course_Framework).

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Recommendation 1

Melissa Pittard (chair), Rachel Saidi, Anna Bargagliotti, Chris Malone

Teach statistics and data science as iterative processes of gleaning insights from data to inform evidence-based decisions.

The following diagram provides a visual of the process of working with data that students in an introductory class should engage in:

Viewing statistics as an iterative process making heavy use of questioning and interrogation of the data is not a new idea (see Lee et al. (2022) for a description of the numerous models of the practice of statistics). For example, Wild and Pfannkuch (1999) present the Problem, Plan, Data, Analysis, Conclusions (PPDAC) model that describes how doing statistics means engaging in a process. The GAISE II K-12 Report (Bargagliotti 2020) also presents the Problem Solving Process, a four-component process that includes Formulating a Question, Collecting or Considering data, Analyzing data, and Interpreting Results. Introductory statistics should convey the seamless integration of statistical methods and the scientific method, how visualizations inform inferential statistical methods, and how inferential statistical methods can lead to new related questions—all through engaging in the process of working with data. Liberal use of examples drawn from real datasets is essential; see [Recommendation 4](#).

The information ecosystem has shifted to a world of consumers and producers of data. This data is used in all aspects of society, such as news and journalism, business and advertising, and policy and healthcare, to name a few fields. Because data is in every facet of our lives, it is important for students to engage in the process of making decisions with data by engaging in the process pictured above. An introductory statistics course can leverage students' innate curiosity and interests to learn more about their world and become more discerning consumers of statistics and data. Students should learn about the iterative nature of how data is collected, what kinds of variables are in question, how to derive questions, how to create visualizations, numerical summaries, and how to perform reproducible inferential statistical procedures to develop insights.

Additional Resources

- [Annotated bibliography](#)
- Examples
- Assessments

Bargagliotti, Anna. 2020. "Pre-k-12 Guidelines for Assessment and Instruction in Statistics Education II (GAISE II)."

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Wild, Chris J, and Maxine Pfannkuch. 1999. "Statistical Thinking in Empirical Enquiry." *International Statistical Review* 67 (3): 223–48.

Recommendation 2

Sara Stoudt (chair), Victor Piercey, Larry Lesser, Dave Hunter

Emphasize effective written and oral communication of results from data, with attention to the scope and limitations of conclusions.

Producing results is only one step in learning from data; students must also communicate their findings clearly and accurately, both orally and in writing. This requires responsiveness to both the genre of communication (i.e., oral or written presentation, journal article, newsletter, conversation with classmates, op-ed, etc.) and the audience background.

Effective communication starts with understanding and conveying the provenance of the data—their source, completeness, validity, relevance, and currency—emphasizing their effect on conclusions. Inferences, visualizations, and analyses should be presented as evidence, not definitive proof, of conclusions. Conclusions drawn from data can yield a better understanding, and [iterations of the process] (<https://amstat.quarto.pub/college-gaise/recommendations/recommendation-01.html>) can continue to improve that understanding. **Ethical communication** requires transparently acknowledging limitations and contextualizing results at an audience-appropriate technical level—**keeping the focus on conceptual understanding**.

Effective communication requires **clarity of purpose**. For example, this purpose could be to inform, influence, problem-solve, motivate, or facilitate dialogue. To aid students in formulating the purpose of their statistical communication, we recommend the mnemonic “genre, audience impact statistical effectiveness.” There is a spectrum of audience background knowledge, ranging from general to more specialized, as well as a spectrum of forms of communication, from the informal or conversational—e.g., blogs or social media—to detailed research reports. Below, we suggest a range of sample activities to provide students with experience communicating along both spectrums.

Audiences also differ in ways other than statistical background knowledge. Their goals and power relations also inform decisions such as the level of detail to communicate and the location of the results in the broader story. Audiences can even be heterogeneous themselves. Students

should also get practice with these nuances as they complete communication activities that span the spectra of audience and genre.

Table 1: Table 1: Sample Activities

	1. Other statisticians	2. Other people with some math literacy (e.g., classmates)	3. Other targeted audience (e.g., policymakers, business people, healthcare professionals)
A: Formal report/presentation	A1	A2	A3
B: Executive summary/memo	B1	B2	B3
C: Opened/persuasive speech	C1	C2	C3
D: Blog post/entertainment item	D1	D2	D3

Meta assignment: Pick an assignment from the list below. Consider what would need to change in the communication approach as the audience moves from 1 to 2, from 2 to 3? What changes as the genre moves from A to B, from B to C, from C to D?

Sample Resource: “5 levels approach” of <https://www.wired.com/video/series/5-levels>

Meta assignment: Pick an assignment from the list below. Consider what would need to change in the communication approach as the audience becomes more mixed. For example, what if you need to write an executive summary for a team with some statisticians and some people with only a baseline math literacy?

A1: Consider the problem of small sample sizes from both a methodological and a representation point of view. Write a formal report or give a formal presentation that communicates answers to the following questions to an audience of other statisticians. What should statisticians be

aware of in terms of the methods they use, and the conclusions they draw? Who may or may not be fully represented in data based on small sample sizes, and what are the implications of not considering these points of view in conclusions drawn from a dataset?

Sample Resource: <https://data-feminism.mitpress.mit.edu/pub/h1w0nbqp/release/3>

Sample Resource: <https://pudding.cool/2020/03/census-history/>

A2: For a piece of writing that you have completed for this class, whether this is an explanation of a p-value in a homework answer or a longer-form piece of writing, exchange responses with a peer and go through a peer review process. (Revise your work based on the feedback you receive.

Sample Resource: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/10691898.2010.11889489>

Sample Resource: <https://dsc-capstone.org/2024-25/assignments/methodology/02/>

A3: For a data analysis that you have completed for this class, give a presentation of your findings to a targeted audience of your choice. Use the time constraint provided by your instructor.

Sample Resource: “5 levels approach” of <https://www.wired.com/video/series/5-levels> Sample Resource: <https://da4all.github.io/student-showcase/>

B1: Write an abstract for a presentation based on a data investigation you have completed, perhaps as a course project. Consider both the space constraint of the abstract itself and the time constraint of the presentation. For example, the Joint Statistical Meetings, a major conference for professional statisticians, has a 1200-character abstract limit (including blank spaces) for a roughly 20-minute talk.

Sample Resource: <https://ww2.amstat.org/meetings/jsm/2025/submissions.cfm> Sample Resource: <https://ww2.amstat.org/meetings/jsm/2022/contributedsessions.cfm>

B2: Explain a topic (such as Simpson’s paradox or the confusion of the inverse) to a non-technical audience such as a policymaker who has familiarity with only the basics of statistics.

Sample Resource: <https://www.allendowney.com/blog/2021/05/25/in-search-of-simpsons-paradox/>

B3: Specify a targeted audience, for example, a decision-maker of some kind, and for a chosen homework question, write a paragraph that communicates the takeaway to that audience.

Sample Resource: <https://da4all.github.io/cards/many-ways-to-write-a-statistic>

C1: Read the ethics codes that are provided, and then draft your own code of ethics, [GAISE College Recommendation 7](#) that you think the statistics and data science community should follow. For at least one element of your code of ethics, defend its inclusion in the code to a group of statisticians who are considering adopting your code.

Sample Resource: <https://www.oreilly.com/radar/of-oaths-and-checklists/> Sample Resource: <https://www.amstat.org/your-career/ethical-guidelines-for-statistical-practice> Sample

Resource: <https://datasciencebydesign.org/blog/writing-a-modelers-manifesto-for-more-transparent-ethical-data-science> Sample Resource: <https://da4all.github.io/cards/write-your-own-data-advocacy-values-statement>

C2: Teach someone with math literacy the importance of data privacy and the limitations of anonymity. Do this by constructing an example where the data seems anonymized, but due to small counts, individuals can be identified. How would you explain this to a researcher who is deciding how to report findings and share data upon publication of their work?

Sample Resource: <https://rss.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/1740-9713.01608>

C3: Choose a dataset, either one we have used in class, [GAISE College Recommendation 4](#) or another that you think is important to be publicly available. Convince a policymaker to support and maintain this dataset as a public good.

Sample Resource: <https://hdsr.mitpress.mit.edu/pub/m3fk4fah/release/2> Sample Resource: <https://www.data-liberation-project.org/>

D1: Consider a software feature or applet, [GAISE College Recommendation 6](#) that you have taken advantage of in this course. Write a blog post tutorial aimed at statisticians who are not yet familiar with the tool that walks them through how to use the tool and explains why it might be useful to them in their work.

Sample Resource: <https://rebeccabarter.com/blog#category=R> Sample Resource: https://lukebenz.com/post/ncaahoopr_v1.5/

D2: Pick a cartoon from the CAUSE Cartoon Caption Contest. This can be the current cartoon or one from the past (no peeking at the winning caption!). Write a caption for it and discuss with a classmate the meaning and effectiveness of the caption for an audience who has some math literacy but not specialized statistical knowledge.

Sample Resource: <https://www.CAUSEweb.org/cause/caption-contest/>

D3: Describe a scenario where two variables are correlated but one does not cause the other. Specify a targeted audience, and create an edutainment piece for that audience that explains the difference in the form of a cartoon, joke, poem, or song.

Sample Resource: <https://www.tylervigen.com/spurious-correlations> Sample Resource: <https://causeweb.org/cause/resources/fun/references>

Additional Resources

- Annotated bibliography
- Examples
- Assessments

Recommendation 3

Nick Horton (chair), Rebecca Wong, Ulrike Genschel, Laura Ziegler, Joe Roith,
Lisa Kay

Emphasize effective written and oral communication of results from data, with attention to the scope and limitations of conclusions.

Introduction: Conceptual vs. Procedural Knowledge

Given the limited time we can devote to instruction, it is essential to prioritize the ideas that we choose to ask our students to engage with. Focusing on conceptual understanding rather than procedural knowledge is fundamental to understanding how and why statistics works.

Focusing on conceptual understanding changes the presentation of topics in the classroom and the types of questions we ask in the classroom and in assessments. We present examples of how conceptual understanding might be centered when presenting two topics from the introductory statistics course: (1) the sample standard deviation and (2) the use of the Empirical Rule.

Conceptual understanding of the standard deviation

One example is understanding the use of the sample standard deviation. Traditionally, instructors might have introduced the standard deviation by providing its formula and asking students to calculate its value for a small sample of observations numerically. This approach focuses on algebraic and procedural skills and may take away from the larger role the standard deviation plays.

An approach focusing more on conceptual understanding and interpretation that might be more effective. We provide two examples:

1. An instructor displays the ages of 5 people on a dot plot with the sample mean marked on the graph. Students are asked, on average, how far are the five ages from the mean age. A discussion about the deviations from the mean is used to describe the standard deviation informally.

Ages: 16, 23, 36, 41, and 59

Distance of five ages from the mean
Standard deviation = 16.7 years

The traditional approach to calculating the sample standard deviation is substantially procedural and may contribute little, if any, towards students' conceptual understanding.

The following example demonstrates one purpose of the standard deviation and will assist students in understanding how to interpret it. Instructors may still show the formula in the second scenario, but instead of plugging the numbers into the formula, students can use technology to compute the standard deviation or simply interpret a provided standard deviation value.

2. Students are given two boxplots, each displaying the final exam scores of all students in two different sections of the same course. Students are asked which section they would expect to have a greater standard deviation and what this might imply practically for an instructor teaching both sections.

Conceptual understanding of the Empirical (68/95/99.7) Rule

Another example is understanding the use of the Empirical Rule. A traditional approach would focus on providing students with the mean and standard deviation of a unimodal symmetric distribution and asking students to compute percentages of the distribution that would fall into various regions. For example, “Scores on a standardized test have a unimodal and symmetric distribution, with a mean of 80 and a standard deviation of 4. What percent of students would we expect to score above 84 on this test?”

Rather than using the Empirical Rule as a tool for computation, a conceptual approach might focus on using the Empirical Rule as a guideline to determine what results could be considered unusual. Smog levels in cities are measured by levels of particulate matter (PM). The distribution of PM in U.S. cities is approximately unimodal and symmetric, with a mean of 7.9 micrograms per cubic meter and a standard deviation of 2.2 micrograms per cubic meter.

1. Would it be unusual for a city to have a PM reading of 11? Why or why not?
2. Which would be more unusual: a PM reading of 3 or a PM reading of 11?
3. Explain and discuss.

The distribution of smog particulate matter (PM) levels in 100 U.S. cities

Mean: 7.9, SD = 2.2

From a statistical perspective, we see little pedagogical value in numerically calculating statistics such as a standard deviation or correlation coefficient by hand. Leveraging and demonstrating the computing tools that implement these formulas can have value and may be considered a special case of [Recommendation 6](#).

Leveraging Technology

Technology is ubiquitous, and trained statisticians rely exclusively on computing. While not every student may have access to technology tools, most do, and it is reasonable to expect that instructors will have access to them. Thus, there is no functional reason for students to practice manual calculations of complex statistical formulas. Consequently, we suggest that manual formulas, algebraic manipulations, and the use of distribution tables are not a priority for an introductory statistics course and should be de-emphasized.

An introductory course will naturally include some computation, and while mathematical language offers a concise way to express key ideas, instructors should introduce only those formulas that enhance conceptual understanding, minimize computations that lack meaningful context, and utilize technology to simplify calculations and analysis.

In addition to using technology for computational purposes, visualization using technology is an effective way to illustrate concepts. Whenever possible, visual demonstration should

be used: for example, visualizing the effect of changing sample size when calculating standard error for the difference in two means. This allows the instructor to touch on the mathematical effects while also keeping the focus on interpreting the data in context. Web applets (e.g., [Rossman/Chance](#), [ISI](#), [StatPREP Little Apps](#), and the [Art of Stat](#)) can help students explore conceptual understanding without having to memorize or use formulas.

Additional pedagogical notes

It is important to recognize that procedural knowledge can work in tandem with conceptual knowledge to strengthen one another (Hurrell, 2021). Procedural knowledge in an introductory statistics course that enhances understanding of concepts should emphasize the statistical process. An example of this includes but is not limited to formulating/recognizing a specific question to be answered using data, identifying variable roles (response/explanatory), determining variable type (quantitative/categorical), exploring relationships through visualizations and summarizations, performing appropriate inferential techniques, and writing interpretations in the context of the original data and question. This approach also better connects the statistical process from one inferential technique to another compared with drawing connections from one formula to another.

Focus on procedural steps, especially with regard to algebraic manipulation and formulas, too often claims students' attention that an effective teacher could otherwise direct toward concepts. An example of this approach may involve providing students with summary statistics and asking them to manually calculate the test statistic and determine the p-value using a t-table. Many students see the calculation of test statistics and using tables to find p-values as the goal, thus undervaluing or completely ignoring the context and purpose of the original question.

Students with a sound conceptual foundation from an introductory course should be able to understand statistics presented in the real world and be well prepared to study additional statistical techniques in a second course. While emphasis may not be placed directly on technical steps, conceptual knowledge gains can lead to procedural knowledge (Rittle-Johnson et al. 2001). By emphasizing concepts and good statistical practices, students will be better adapted to handle new statistical situations outside of the classroom.

Suggestions for teachers

- View the primary goal as to discover and apply concepts.
- Focus on students' understanding of key concepts, illustrated by a few techniques, rather than covering a multitude of techniques with minimal focus on underlying ideas.
- Pare down the content of an introductory course to focus on core concepts in more depth.
- Perform most computations using technology to allow greater emphasis on understanding concepts and interpreting results.

- Although the language of mathematics provides a compact expression of key ideas, use formulas that enhance the understanding of concepts and avoid computations that are divorced from understanding.
- Use visual methods when demonstrating concepts instead of mathematical methods whenever possible.

Additional Resources

- [Annotated bibliography](#)
- Examples
- [Assessments](#)

Rittle-Johnson, Bethany, Robert S Siegler, and Martha Wagner Alibali. 2001. "Developing Conceptual Understanding and Procedural Skill in Mathematics: An Iterative Process." *Journal of Educational Psychology* 93 (2): 346.

Recommendation 4

Rob Gould, Robin Lock, Ambika Silva (chair), Jennifer Broatch, Jamie Perrett

Integrate real data with a context and purpose throughout the course. Select data that are meaningful and engaging to the students.

Real data refers to datasets from genuine, practical situations, showing the complexity and variety of data we encounter daily. Integrating real data into a statistics course bridges the gap between abstract concepts and practical applications, making learning more engaging and relevant. By selecting datasets related to topics students care about—such as social issues, sports, health, or the environment—students can explore meaningful questions while developing statistical skills (Willett and Singer 1992).

What makes data “real”? To some extent, this depends on the instructional purpose of the data. Students need to engage in authentic problem-solving and learn to extract meaning from data. This can, in part, be achieved by providing clear context for each dataset, including its origins and purpose. Students also need experience working with data with different variable types, and with different sources such as survey data, experimental results, observational data, or business metrics. Real data sets can provide authentic opportunities for students to connect their analysis to real-world problem-solving. This approach encourages critical thinking, creativity, and engagement, preparing students to use statistics as a tool for understanding complex, real-world challenges that also relate to their personal pursuits, past experiences, and cultural traditions (Louie et al. 2021).

Using real data serves both curricular and pedagogical goals. Curricularly, it emphasizes problem-solving over rote application or theoretical study, ensuring students learn to evaluate statistical claims, pose investigative questions, and connect statistics to their field of study. Pedagogically, working with real or realistic data exposes students to challenges they will encounter in authentic analyses, such as missing values or non-standard distributions. Realistic data can be simulated datasets designed to mimic patterns and challenges of authentic data, providing controlled yet realistic learning opportunities. While simplified and/or simulated datasets can be useful for focused teaching moments, the integration of real data provides the depth and complexity needed to prepare students for future work in data analysis. Additionally,

real data can enhance student engagement, as it provides opportunities for students to examine contexts that they're interested in (Neumann et al. 2013).

To access real data, instructors can explore online repositories, textbook datasets, or classroom-generated data from activities or surveys. Many modern textbooks include relevant, well-formatted datasets, and collaborative efforts with colleagues across disciplines can provide additional sources. Data sources and webpages specifically geared toward education can also simplify the process of finding and using meaningful datasets. By integrating these resources, educators can help students build statistical expertise while solving real-world problems. Integrating real data enables students to develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills while applying statistical methods in meaningful, applied contexts.

Real data may include some or all of these key characteristics:

1. **Authenticity:** Collected for actual purposes, such as research, decision-making, or operational processes, rather than being artificially created solely for instructional use. Authenticity can be enhanced by asking meaningful investigative questions, such as those questions for which the data were initially collected.
2. **Relevance:** Connected to topics or issues that are meaningful and relatable for students, such as public health, climate change, sports analytics, social trends, or themselves.
3. **Complexity (when necessary):** May include features commonly encountered in practical analysis, such as missing values, outliers, non-linear relationships, and varied distributions.
4. **Contextual Depth:** Accompanied by clear explanations of its origins, purpose, and the questions it seeks to address, helping learners understand its significance and practical application.

Additional Resources

- Annotated bibliography
- [Examples](#)
- Assessments

Louie, Josephine, Jennifer Stiles, Emily Fagan, Soma Roy, and Beth Chance. 2021. "Data Investigations to Further Social Justice Inside and Outside of STEM." *Connected Science Learning* 3 (1): 12318679.

Neumann, David L, Michelle Hood, and Michelle M Neumann. 2013. "Using Real-Life Data When Teaching Statistics: Student Perceptions of This Strategy in an Introductory Statistics Course." *Statistics Education Research Journal* 12 (2): 59–70.

Willett, John B, and Judith D Singer. 1992. "Providing a Statistical Model': Teaching Applied Statistics Using Real-World Data." *Statistics for the Twenty-First Century* 26: 83–98.

Recommendation 5

Kelly McConville (chair), Ben Baumer, Nathan Tintle, Mine Dogucu, Patti Frazer
Lock

Encourage multivariate thinking.

Introduction

Multivariable thinking (MVT) is critical for students to be able to navigate our complex, data-driven world. Phenomena in areas such as economics, medicine, social sciences, and natural sciences are influenced by a multitude of factors, and many rich data sets with lots of cases and a great number of variables are readily available. MVT is no longer a skill required only of statisticians and data scientists—everyone should be able to think critically about the relationships among many variables and draw conclusions from that investigation.

MVT is not new to statistics, or even new to the introductory statistics course. However, we must do more than sprinkle traces of MVT in our courses. Rather, we must embrace the inherent complexity of MVT and ensure that students get repeated practice disentangling the relationships in data. MVT is needed throughout the data analysis process and is necessary for understanding current research in applied disciplines such as medicine (NJ 2005) and countless others across the natural and social sciences and beyond. Multiple regression is just one technique for engaging with MVT. More broadly, MVT can span multiple units in introductory classes, including exploratory data analysis, statistical modeling, and statistical inference. In this section, we provide concrete suggestions on how to infuse MVT into introductory statistics and data science courses.

First steps towards MVT

Here are some starting points for incorporating MVT into your classes:

- Even if you focus on one or two variables in a study in order to help students master key learning objectives, go beyond this and require students to reflect on the broader context in which the datasets exist. (Assessment examples/resources: Problem 1 of [this document](#))

- Regularly ask your students to create/find, explore and summarize datasets that have multiple variables. (Assessment examples/resources: First day survey example, [student generated game data](#) as explained in depth by Kuiper et al. (2025), problem 2 of [this document](#))
- Provide opportunities for students to interpret and create data visualizations that display more than two variables. This, for example, can be achieved simply by coloring points on a scatterplot to represent a third variable. (Assessment examples/resources: Problem 3 of [this document](#), [NYTimes “What’s going on in this graph?”](#), [Gapminder Tools](#), [this applet](#))
- Ask students to identify potential confounding variables and brainstorm how the impact of additional variables could possibly affect their conclusions. Exploring an example that exhibits Simpson’s Paradox can provide a compelling case for the importance of MVT. (Assessment examples/resources: [How Much Do Minority Lives Matter?](#))

Intermediate topics related to MVT

Most of our first steps involved considering how additional variables might impact one’s statistical work. For the intermediate steps, we suggest requiring students to more directly incorporate multiple variables into their analysis:

- Infuse MVT into your lessons about data collection methods. Ask students to brainstorm what potential confounding variables they would like to measure, or how they might employ stratification in random sampling. (Assessment examples/resources: [Section 7.3.1 of “Using data-centric methods to teach introductory statistics”](#))
- Ask students to explore how common data wrangling steps, such as removing observations with missing values or transforming variables, impact the relationships between variables in their datasets. (Assessment examples/resources: [Section 7.3.2 of “Using data-centric methods to teach introductory statistics”](#))
- For student projects, get students asking and assessing MVT questions, such as how to control for variables and what potential confounding variables exist. (Assessment examples/resources:)
- Lay the foundation for modeling by helping students see connections between the two-sample t-test and the linear regression model. (Assessment examples/resources: [This activity](#))
- Take a prediction approach to motivate and teach the idea of multiple linear regression. In particular, have students (Assessment examples/resources:)
 - Explore these models graphically by creating scatterplots where a third categorical variable is represented by the color of the points and include the regression curve.
 - Fit these models and use them for prediction.

- Consider the assumptions of the model and whether or not any violated assumptions could be resolved by incorporating additional predictors.
- Connect the interpretation of individual model terms with the idea of confounding.

Aspirational topics related to MVT

We understand that many introductory statistics courses are already overloaded with topics to cover. Given the importance of MVT to modern data work, we recommend instructors take a hard look at what topics can be removed to make room for more MVT. (Our suggestions might include looking up p-values in tables, calculating the standard deviation by hand, or deriving closed form expressions for the expected value of a random variable mathematically.) A few aspirational topics to consider including in your courses include:

- Have students brainstorm sources of variation in a response variable before giving them access to the data. Ask students to determine whether these sources of variation could be controlled by design or analytically or if these sources need to remain as unexplained variation? (Assessment examples/resources: [this exploration](#))
- Continue developing the student’s understanding of multiple linear regression. In particular, have students (Assessment examples/resources: [this activity](#), [this app](#))
 - Graphically explore the differences between equal slopes and different slopes models.
 - Practice interpreting interaction terms between categorical and quantitative predictors.
 - Conduct inference for regression terms.
 - Use a model selection criteria, such as adjusted R-squared or BIC, to compare and evaluate different models.

Additional Resources

- Annotated bibliography
- [Examples](#)
- Assessments

Kuiper, Shonda, Abhishek Chakraborty, Tyler George, et al. 2025. “The Greenhouse Effect: Using Student-Generated Agricultural Data to Warm up Students for Data-Based Decision Making.” *Journal of Statistics and Data Science Education* 33 (2): 143–51.

NJ, HORTON. 2005. “Statistical Methods in the Journal.” *N Engl J Med.* 353 (18): 1977–79.

Recommendation 6

Hunter Glanz (chair), Michael Sullivan, Amelia McNamara, Patti Frazer Lock

Incorporate software/apps to explore concepts and work with data.

Introductory Statistics

All students in an Introductory Statistics course should be exposed to a statistical software package or statistical apps, beyond graphing calculators. We do not prescribe any specific technology, since course goals, student audiences, and institutional constraints will differ. Using technology to create graphs, provide summary statistics, and handle much of the inferential analysis allows instructors to spend significantly more time on interpretation and on helping students garner insight from data. In addition, technology can be a powerful way to develop student understanding of the key ideas of statistics and data science. Technology is integral to data science, and essential to doing any type of data analysis.

Choose the technology based on the learning outcomes of the course. Technology has the benefit of creating a more equitable course. Algebraic and computational skills creates an unnecessary barrier to successfully complete the Introductory Stats or Data Science course.

There are many things to consider when determining what software to use in your course, and we discuss some of these considerations here. We provide a list of free online statistical applets [here](#).

Assessment can be challenging when it comes to the use of technology. We address this issue [here](#), where we provide a wide variety of help with assessment options.

Software Selection Link

When Fisher published *Statistical Methods for Research Workers*, he understood the importance of facilitating calculations to make statistical methods more accessible. Fisher also understood that statistical computations would become easier with the advent of technology. The purpose of a statistical course is not to get bogged down in calculation, but to use models to develop an understanding of the world through data. Statistical software allows for students to analyze

data frames with many observations and variables. This presents students with a more realistic scenario than simply working only with data sets that have a single variable with a few observations.

Technology via statistical spreadsheets and applets also allows students to develop conceptual understanding of statistical ideas quickly via data visualization, simulation, bootstrapping, and randomization. These tools lessen the concern of doing calculation and increase the benefit of seeing the power of statistics.

- **Data Visualization** discuss how software should be utilized to easily generate graphs beyond just simple boxplots. But allow for engagement and multiple variables. For example, easily identify outliers in a data frame from the graph. Provide graphs with multiple variables.
- **Simulation**
 - Statistical software should be used to simulate sampling from data frames so that statistical concepts may be developed. For example, obtain 1000 simple random samples from a data frame for a particular quantitative variable for various sample sizes. Compute the sample mean for each sample and describe the shape, center, spread of the sample mean to illustrate sampling distributions.
 - Also discuss simulation for introducing hypothesis test for a proportion.
 - Applets here??
- **Bootstrapping**
- **Randomization** Discuss how statistical software allows for an introduction to

Statistical Applets Link

Assessment Link: Assessment is broadly categorized as either [formative](#) or [summative](#). Here, we provide suggestions for how technology may be incorporated for each of these assessment methods.

- **Formative Assessment**
 - Consider the use of personal response systems (PRS). PRS may be used to develop an active learning environment. The advantage of using PRS is that they increase engagement, encourage peer-to-peer instruction, and allow the instructor to target lectures as a result of the immediate feedback. A leading expert of using peer-to-peer instruction in classrooms is Eric Mazur of Harvard University. Here is an [article](#) on using peer-to-peer instruction. Even though Eric is a professor of physics, his methods apply to Introductory Statistics course as well. Here are some YouTube videos of Dr. Mazur's thoughts:

- * [Assessment: The Silent Killer of Learning](#)
- * [Peer Instruction](#)
- Allow for more in-depth assignments that utilize large data frames. For example, provide a large data frame and ask students to determine the best explanatory variable for a given response variable based on the correlation coefficient. Build a linear model utilizing that explanatory variable.
- Consider the use of course management systems that algorithmically generate homework problems for students. These systems typically provide instant feedback to students along with learning aids that help students learn how to solve statistical problems.
- **Summative Assessment** This assessment method can be a challenge for instructors who do not have access to labs with computers. However, there are techniques that may be utilized in this environment even without the use of hand-held technology.
 - Focus should be more on the interpretation of statistical results as opposed to the producing statistical results. Use screen captures of statistical output to interpret results. For example, provide output of a least-squares regression for a statistical problem and ask a variety of questions regarding the output such as (i) state the correlation coefficient (ii) state the least-squares regression equation, (iii) make predictions (iv) ask students to determine whether a particular observation is above or below average for a particular value of the explanatory variable, and so on. The instructor could also provide graphs such as residual plots to assess the linear model (outliers, appropriateness of the linear model, and so on).
 - Provide multiple screen captures. Require the student to identify the correct output before interpreting results. For example, provide a scenario that requires a hypothesis test on a proportion. Provide output that performs a hypothesis test for $H_0 : p < p_0$, $H_0 : p \neq p_0$, and $H_0 : p > p_0$. Perhaps even provide output for $H_0 : p < \hat{p}$, and so on. Ask students to verify model requirements, identify the p-value, state a conclusion using the correct output.

Introductory Data Science

All students in an Introductory Data Science course should be exposed to a statistical software package, coding language, or statistical apps, beyond graphing calculators. We do not prescribe any specific technology, since course goals, student audiences, and institutional constraints will differ. Using technology to create graphs, provide summary statistics, and handle much of the modeling allows instructors to spend significantly more time on interpretation and on helping students garner insight from data. In addition, technology can be a powerful way to develop student understanding of the key ideas of data science.

There are many things to consider when determining what software to use in your course, and we discuss some of these considerations here. We provide a list of free online statistical applets here.

Assessment can be challenging when it comes to the use of technology. We address this issue here, where we provide a wide variety of help with assessment options.

Software Selection Link

When Fisher published *Statistical Methods for Research Workers*, he understood the importance of facilitating calculations to make statistical methods more accessible. Fisher also understood that statistical computations would become easier with the advent of technology. The purpose of a data science course is not to get bogged down in calculation, but to use models to develop an understanding of the world through data. Statistical software allows for students to analyze data frames with many observations and variables. This presents students with a more realistic scenario than simply working only with data sets that have a single variable with a few observations.

Technology via coding, spreadsheet software, and applets also allows students to develop conceptual understanding of data science ideas quickly via data wrangling, summarization, visualization, and modeling. These tools lessen the concern of doing calculation and increase the benefit of seeing the power of data science.

- **Data Wrangling** discuss how software should be utilized to clean and prepare data for summarization, visualization, and analysis.
- **Data Summarization** discuss how software should be utilized to summarize data in univariate and multivariate ways to uncover relationships and identify possible needs for more wrangling.
- **Data Visualization** discuss how software should be utilized to easily generate graphs beyond just simple boxplots. But allow for engagement and multiple variables. For example, easily identify outliers in a data frame from the graph. Also, how this informs possible needs for more wrangling. Provide graphs with multiple variables.
- **Data Modeling** discuss how software should be utilized to model relationships between a response variable and one or more explanatory variables.

Statistical Applets Link

Assessment Link: Assessment is broadly categorized as either [formative](#) or [summative](#). Here, we provide suggestions for how technology may be incorporated for each of these assessment methods.

- **Formative Assessment**

- Consider the use of personal response systems (PRS). PRS may be used to develop an active learning environment. The advantage of using PRS is that they increase engagement, encourage peer-to-peer instruction, and allow the instructor to target lectures as a result of the immediate feedback. A leading expert of using peer-to-peer instruction in classrooms is Eric Mazur of Harvard University. Here is an [article](#) on using peer-to-peer instruction. Even though Eric is a professor of physics, his methods apply to Introductory Data Science course as well. Here are some YouTube videos of Dr. Mazur's thoughts:

- * [Assessment: The Silent Killer of Learning](#)

- * [Peer Instruction](#)

- Allow for more in-depth assignments that utilize large data frames. For example, provide a large data frame and ask students to determine the best explanatory variable for a given response variable based on visualizations. Build a regression or nonparametric model (e.g. decision tree) to model and assess the relationship.
- Consider the use of course management systems that algorithmically generate homework problems for students. These systems typically provide instant feedback to students along with learning aids that help students learn how to solve statistical problems.

- **Summative Assessment** This assessment method can be a challenge for instructors who do not have access to labs with computers. However, there are techniques that may be utilized in this environment even without the use of hand-held technology.

- Use screen captures of data science output to interpret results. For example, provide output of a least-squares regression application and ask a variety of questions regarding the output such as (i) state the correlation coefficient (ii) state the least-squares regression equation, (iii) make predictions (iv) ask students to determine whether a particular observation is above or below average for a particular value of the explanatory variable, and so on. The instructor could also provide graphs such as residual plots to assess the linear model (outliers, appropriateness of the linear model, and so on).

Provide multiple screen captures. Require the student to identify the correct output before interpreting results.

Additional Resources

- Annotated bibliography

- Examples
- Assessments

Recommendation 7

Judith Canner (chair), Matthew Hayat, Jessica Utts, Donna Lalonde

Emphasize responsible and ethical conduct in the collection and use of data and in their analysis.

Ethics must be integrated and discussed at every stage of the statistics and data science process to ensure trustworthy results and minimize risk to others. The complex technology landscape coupled with an increasing availability of real-world data makes it essential that statistics and data science instruction incorporate the ethical aspects of data collection, analysis, and dissemination of results (Raman et al. 2023). As articulated in the Ethical Guidelines for Statistical Practice as published by the American Statistical Association (2022), “Good statistical practice is fundamentally based on transparent assumptions, reproducible results, and valid interpretations.” The following outlines the process of statistics and data science with an emphasis on integrating ethical discussion throughout.

1. **Formulate a Research Question:** The first step in any research is to formulate a question or questions, and to determine whether appropriate data collection methods are available. The discussion can include issues such as whether a large enough sample can be collected to provide meaningful results, and whether the study has ecological validity (i.e., mimics how treatments would be applied in the real world as opposed to in an experiment). As we integrate data with context and purpose instructors can demonstrate ways that data can be used for good (e.g., identify equity gaps for intervention) or for oppression (e.g., facial recognition, inappropriate use of private data).
2. **Data Collection and Preparation:** The ethicality of data collection and preparation can include the following issues.
 - a. Were the data collection methods appropriate for the research question(s)?
 - b. Is there reason to question the accuracy of the data based on how and from whom they were collected?
 - c. Is there reason to think that the data may be biased or cause misleading results, for instance if dropout rates differed among treatment groups?

- d. Was appropriate consent given? If the data are from human subjects, did they give permission for their data to be used this way, for instance to be shared publicly or to be used for a purpose other than that stated in the original informed consent?
 - e. Are appropriate measures being taken to ensure data protection and confidentiality?
 - f. How will data cleaning, handling missing data, and transforming data impact our results, and have all such steps been documented?
3. **Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA):** In addition to data visualization and software tools, students should be able to discuss the ethics of data representation - relating–relating back to how to appropriately answer a research question, choosing the right statistic(s) to address the question, making comparisons when groups differ at baseline, and other ways EDA could be misused or misinterpreted (e.g., [Prison COVID Cases Fuel New Rural Hotspot; State’s Map Draws Criticism | Georgia Public Broadcasting](#); [Visualizing the Virus](#)). In addition, this step can be used to discuss virtue ethics, such as compassionate data visualization - how–how do we communicate both the humanity and reality of the data in a visualization?
 4. **Analysis:** In model development, discussions about selecting appropriate data analysis or modeling methods based on data are important as students consider the limitations of inference and the assumptions underlying the modelling method. Every analysis should be reproducible¹([New Report Examines Reproducibility and Replicability in Science, Recommends Ways to Improve Transparency and Rigor in Research | National Academies](#)) .
 5. **Drawing Conclusions and Communicating Results:** Presentation of results should include statements related to causality and the generalizability of the results. For example, 1) how does data collection limit how the results can be generalized?, 2) can we use the analysis to make reliable predictions?, 3) who is responsible for how others use a model or result? 4) is the full story presented, or are only the most striking results presented, thus increasing the likelihood of a false positive?
 6. **Considering Changes in Data and Technology:** In practice, one of the most important steps in both data science and statistics is recognizing that they are iterative processes. The acquisition of new knowledge may require the modification of initial findings. Data and analysis may need to be revisited, and decisions based on inference may need to be reformulated in different contexts or under varying conditions.

The field of statistics is changing, and with these changes come new ethical imperatives in statistics education. As Rameela Raman, Jessica Utts, Andrew Cohen, and Matthew Hayat write in a 2023 article in *The American Statistician*, “with technological advancement and the increase in availability of real-world datasets, it is necessary that instruction also integrate the

¹Reproducibility in analysis requires that all computational analyses, when repeated on the same data, produce consistent results.

ethical aspects around data sources, such as privacy, how the data were obtained and whether participants consent to the use of their data.”

Additional Resources

- Annotated bibliography
- Examples
- Assessments

Raman, Rameela, Jessica Utts, Andrew I Cohen, and Matthew J Hayat. 2023. “Integrating Ethics into the Guidelines for Assessment and Instruction in Statistics Education (GAISE).” *The American Statistician* 77 (3): 323–30.

Recommendation 8

Beth Chance (chair), Hollylynn Lee, Amanda Ellis, Anelise Sabbag, Jamie Perrett

Employ evidence-based pedagogies that actively engage students in the learning process.

Studies have shown that students learn more when they are actively involved in the learning process (e.g., Felder and Brent 2024; Lombardi et al. 2021; National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine 2025). Rather than passively receiving information, students can construct their own understandings and connections, reflect on their level of understanding, share their thinking with other students and the instructor, explore new ideas, and test conjectures (Sciences et al. 2018). Learning statistics should happen in an environment where teachers continually put students at the center of the learning experience. Courses in statistics and data science offer many natural opportunities for such engagement, whether using manipulatives to make abstract ideas concrete, asking students to make predictions and then use technology to test their understanding, or having students design and carry out full data collection projects from framing the question to presenting their conclusions.

Every class session can include some opportunities for students to actively engage. These opportunities can be very quick additions to your existing courses and class meetings do not have to be 100% activity-based to achieve active engagement. In fact, interspersing activity-learning with lecture may be beneficial in providing students with variety and reinforcement. Below we offer some strategies and examples of steps you can take. Keep in mind that not all active learning strategies work for all course content or for all students, but a variety of experiences beyond passive lecture can make the course more engaging and meaningful for the students and for you! We are not suggesting that you should never lecture, but try to make those lectures more student-centered and consider placing the lecture after students have experienced some productive struggle with a new concept.

Principles and strategies for adding more active pedagogies to your classroom

- **Incorporating active engagement in the classroom does not require a complete course redesign.** Small, intentional changes—such as interactive discussions, brief

in-class activities, or opportunities for reflection—can have a positive impact on student learning and engagement. Even minor adjustments to course materials provided to students (e.g., leaving key words out of a definition to fill in together; allowing time for students to brainstorm an application of a statistics technique; think-pair-share; jigsaw) can enhance understanding and foster a more dynamic, student-centered learning environment (Corbo and Sasaki 2021).

- **Tailor activities to the students.** Active engagement can support learning with all ages of students, from elementary to graduate-level (Sciences et al. 2018). When incorporating active engagement in the classroom, consider the audience of the course. Activities that resonate with an introductory statistics course for nursing students may differ from those suited for business majors, primarily in terms of context and students' background knowledge and goals for the course. Ask questions purposefully and based on your students' background knowledge—starting with easier questions to build confidence before progressing to more complex discussions—to encourage deeper thinking and participation. To support learning, provide scaffolding—such as optional videos—and create opportunities for questioning, revision, and further exploration.
- **Involve as many students as possible.** Consider ways of getting more students to share their knowledge. This can range from gently calling on students (with an option to “pass”) to asking students to covertly hold up one, two, or three fingers in response to a multiple choice question, to using online polls or classroom response systems (e.g., Muir et al. 2020). For example, if you have students present to the class, consider requiring other students to ask questions of the presenter; if you only have one computer, consider asking different students to run the software with another student telling them what to do, and a third student commenting on what they did.
- **Be prepared.** Not all class data collection or learn-by-doing activities will be successful, so try to build in contingency plans. For example, consider having data from the previous class handy to supplement what's collected in class. To help evaluate an activity, work through the activity yourself, playing the role of student, prior to using it in class. After class, jot down notes from your experiences/student comments to suggest improvements for the next iteration.
- **Embrace the uncertainty.** Implementing active engagement can feel uncomfortable for instructors, as it often involves an element of uncertainty in how class discussion will proceed or how a class activity will end (e.g., exactly how data collected in class will turn out). Acknowledging this uncertainty and participating alongside students can foster deeper engagement. Let students know that not having all the answers is part of the learning process and that figuring things out together is a valuable skill.
- **Consider the important role of student-to-student interaction.** Don't underestimate how much students can learn from each other. Students wrangling over an idea with each other and defending their reasoning can be a powerful learning tool, especially in the

absence of an “expert” providing answers. A small step (and good starting point) is assigning students to a small group in class and asking them to submit a single group answer that incorporates everyone’s viewpoint. A larger step could be a long-term out-of-class group project, with periodic check-in points throughout the term. Research has shown that building in a collaborative structure, with individual accountability and positive interdependence, can be key to achieving effective and enriching learning opportunities (e.g, Cohen and Lotan 2014; Johnson and Johnson 2009). It is also important to have clear guidelines to encourage positive and respectful interactions (e.g. make/take space, listen to each other, use “I” statements). For longer collaborations, provide students with opportunities to evaluate each other; this allows instructors to identify any group challenges early and support students in overcoming difficulties effectively.

- **Be sensitive to students’ personal situations.** Whether it is collecting data on students or asking students to work in groups, active engagement can feel uncomfortable for some. Student engagement often increases when examining data on themselves, but be sure to collect data anonymously and even consider whether some demographic questions are truly necessary. Group work can be successful when the instructor supports students as they interact with each other, e.g., discussing the purpose of active engagement, setting clear expectations, and fostering open conversations about goals (Johnson and Johnson 2009). Additionally, consider effective group dynamics and find ways to better support the needs of all students (c.f., Felder and Brent 2024; National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine 2025). But even with a very good and supportive structure, not all students may feel comfortable participating in group activities or presenting in front of the class, so consider alternative ways for them to engage or provide mechanisms for a student to opt out of certain activities (Gin et al. 2020).
- **Be a proactive facilitator of learning.** When students are engaging with each other and doing something active, the role of the instructor changes to monitoring and intervening if/when needed. If you give students time to work on a longer activity, be visible around the room, stop, listen, and ask students questions, but encourage them to ask each other questions before asking you. Consider putting “stop signs” in the middle of an activity requiring them to check in with you before proceeding. Try to give yourself time to debrief an activity at the end of class or at the beginning of the next class period and/or ask students to share their reflections in a discussion board. See your role as facilitator of learning rather than provider of all knowledge (Morrison 2014).
- **An activity can accomplish the same learning goals in a similar amount of time as a lecture.** Instructors often think they don’t have time to add a non-lecture component to their class; but consider replacing a lecture-based portion of class or instructor-led demonstration with a student-led exploration or a student-collected dataset (Lombardi et al. 2021). You can also consider moving some of the “background” reading/review to outside of class (e.g., pre-lab, reading and videos) to help students prepare for getting the most out of time together in class, this is sometimes referred to a “flipped” classroom (Farmus et al. 2020). Also have conversations with the students about the instructional

purpose of an activity and encourage thoughtful reflection on the connections to the associated learning goals.

- **Give students choice and ownership.** You probably can't go as far as involving students in selecting course topics or having a student's question determine the content discussed that day, but you can look for ways to provide students' choice and ownership (Cook-Sather et al. 2014). For example, when using a large multivariate dataset, allow students the choice of which quantitative variables they want to explore relationships among when learning about correlation and least squares regression. For a final project, you can allow students to choose the research question and design the data collection plan they will carry out. On an exam, you can give them a choice of datasets with the same analysis goals or a choice of exam questions of similar difficulty.
- **Engaging learners can also occur in online environments.** Opportunities for students to construct their own knowledge as well as to interact with each other and work collaboratively can enhance the learning process in online courses as well (e.g, Everson and Garfield 2008; Mills and Raju 2011). Even in an asynchronous setting, techniques such as Collaborative Keys (e.g., Sabbag et al. 2025) and Discussion Forums (e.g., Lima et al. 2019) can incorporate key elements of cooperative learning. For example, well-designed discussion board prompts (e.g., critiquing an article) and requiring students to respond to other posts (e.g., code review) or asking students to use voice and video tools to engage with each other, can build a sense of community among students and the instructor. You can also enhance engagement with online material by asking specific questions related to content at different timestamps instead of having students passively watch a video.

Additional Resources

- Annotated bibliography
- Examples
- Assessments

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Recommendation 9

Julie Neisler (chair), Andy Zieffler, Matt Beckman, Jennifer Ward, Kate Kozak

Use a variety of formative and summative assessments to improve teaching and learning.

Effective teachers use assessment for making instructional decisions, motivating students, providing them with feedback about their learning, and measuring performance. Classroom assessment can be typically categorized as formative assessment or summative assessment, depending on the instructor's purpose for administering the assessment. [Formative Assessment](#) can be described as **assessment to assist learning** (e.g., primarily used for [Feedback](#)), while [Summative Assessment](#) is best described as **assessment of learning** (e.g., evaluation, part of a student's grade). Because the goals or purposes of formative and summative assessment are markedly different, the assessment process (e.g., timeline for administration, feedback) needs to be viewed differently by both instructors and learners.

We've also summarized additional information on [Additional Considerations for Assessment](#), including [Assessment in the Age of Advancing Technology](#) (e.g., AI).

Formative Assessment

The primary goal of formative assessment is to assist student learning by providing [feedback](#) intended to modify the learning or instructional process (Black and Wiliam 1998). In particular, it needs to be administered at points where it is critical for instructors and students to ensure that students are progressing as expected. Importantly, the type of [feedback provided on a formative assessment] needs to help students adjust their thinking or behavior to improve learning (Shute 2008), though students may need scaffolding when translating feedback to adjustments. Feedback can be provided in many different forms, “from verbal responses given in class, to thoughtful, written feedback on students' work” (Ruiz-Primo et al. 2010), but needs to be non-evaluative (Harrison et al. 2014), timely (Fisher et al. 2025), and specific to the cognitive task being assessed.

In addition to the benefits to students, evidence from student responses on formative assessment can help instructors make student-informed decisions during the instructional process. Metaphorically, instruction and curriculum are the teacher's planned roadmap for taking learners from where they currently are to where the instructor wants them to be. Formative assessment can then be viewed as a real-time Google Maps, offering real-time data to instructors about when it is necessary to deviate from the original plan to better equip students to make the cognitive destination. Additionally, well thought out formative assessments can provide instructors with task-specific feedback about their students' understanding. For example, evidence from formative assessment might highlight that students are struggling with a particular part of hypothesis testing (e.g., always measuring p-values as one-sided) which helps target instructional intervention. Research has shown that using formative assessment data to modify instruction or providing students with individualized feedback significantly positively impacts student outcomes (Formica et al. 2010; Huberth et al. 2015).

Instructors should use a variety of formative assessments (e.g., [thumbs up/thumbs down], [discussions at tables], clicker questions, [think-pair-shares], [taking votes], having [students argue ideas]). Not only does this help prepare students for the array of nonstandard problems they will encounter in the "real-world," but it also helps provide students with a deeper and more robust understanding of the content. Additionally, employing different methods of formative assessment may improve students' sense of belonging by allowing them to engage with the material in multiple ways.

Feedback

Feedback on formative and summative assessment is necessary for informing student learning. However, this brings up some concepts that need to be explored. These include but are not limited to

- How do we give feedback well
- How do we use feedback to improve student learning

Actionable feedback on formative assessment is an important part of teaching. It can be used to give your students direction of where their thinking is along a productive track and when they may need to change their thought process. It is also useful for the instructor to inform where their teaching has been effective and what they may need to find another approach. There has been some research in higher education on how this feedback is helpful. Following is an exploration of some of the research.

It is important to note that not all feedback is helpful, and some may be detrimental. "Effective feedback should indicate what the learning goals are; what progress is being made toward the goal; and what activities need to be undertaken to make better progress." (Barana et al. 2021).

Another aspect of feedback is that it should be “sum up that effective formative feedback should be ‘timely, constructive, motivational, personal, manageable, and directly related to assessment criteria and learning outcomes’” (Fisher et al. 2025). If the feedback is not given in time for the students to use it for other formative assessment and for summative assessment, then the feedback is not useful. So when giving feedback, think about how the students will use it, assess the content and not the person, and make sure that it provides enough information for improvement but isn’t so long that the feedback you are giving is not lost in the wording.

Feedback is important in helping a student become a confident learner. Culturally responsive feedback has properties that provide tools for students to become confident learners (Ferlazzo 2025). These properties are:

- State your confidence in the student’s ability to master this concept, process or skills (“I know you are a very capable student.”)
- Point out explicitly what the student got right and where he went wrong. (Here is where things got off track...”)
- Name specific actions he needs to take (i.e., review the steps, learn the procedure , etc.) (“How would you fix that? Here’s where I’d like you to go back and review,” or “When you get to this part, rethink this move here...”)
- Re-affirm your belief in the student’s capacity and effort to reach the target (i.e., “You got this...”)

The use of feedback on summative assessment in higher education needs more research. There is some research that shows that feedback on summative assessment is not very useful. In order for feedback to be useful according to Harrison et al. (2014), a learner

- needs to be receptive to receiving it. Secondly,
- must understand the message being given, so it must be such that it aligns with the learner’s frame of reference (Kluger and DeNisi 1996),
- needs to set concrete, meaningful and attainable goals, and then take steps to reach them (Harrison et al. 2014).

However, all feedback whether it is on formative or summative assessments should be actionable. This means that the student can learn from the feedback to learn the topics either for future assessments or just general knowledge. In conclusion, all feedback should be timely, direct, readable, and actionable. Every teacher wants a student to learn and feedback should be part of the learning environment.

Summative Assessment

The primary goal of summative assessments is to gather evidence for the purposes of making evaluative judgments about the student’s learning (Cizek et al. 2019), and, subsequently, their grades. Traditionally these take the form of homework, quizzes, and exams, although [many alternatives] have been proposed in the literature (e.g., projects, performance-based tasks).

The key to labeling assessment as summative is not the form the assessment takes, but that it is used to compute a final grade.

Summative assessment should always be coherently integrated with curriculum and instruction. This means that content included on a summative assessment needs to align with the learning outcomes in a course and with content from formative assessments. Because instructors only assess a sample of the course content, assessment items should reflect content that is important, because students make value judgments about what is assessed and what isn't (Biggs et al. 2022; Wiggins 1998)

It is also important to clearly communicate expectations and performance standards to students. Providing instructions and guidelines for responding in sufficient detail and answering questions that arise will help prevent confusion and furnish more accurate evidence about students' learning. This also means making the content, skills, and knowledge students will be evaluated on transparent to them, including the criteria used to make these evaluations. Creating and, when possible, sharing rubrics for evaluation of students' performance helps with this transparency and also ensures equity for all students.

Protip: The formative assessment process can be used to familiarize students with expectations for performance on summative assessments! (Dobson 2008)

Additional Considerations for Assessment

Successful implementation of formative and summative assessments requires instructors to consider many aspects of their teaching environment. Course characteristics and institutional constraints often influence the choice of and application of formative and summative assessments. This following list, although not exhaustive, highlights several factors that instructors might consider when planning their assessment portfolio.

- **Institutional policies.** Consider what policies your institution or department has in place regarding assessment.
 - Are face-to-face (or proctored) exams required?
 - What technology are students allowed to use on assessments?
 - Are students required to use lock-down browsers during assessments?
- **Class size.** How many students will be assessed? Will feedback be given to each individual student or general feedback summarized for the class?
- **Course modality.** Are students taking an in-person class, an online class, or a class that's a hybrid of online and in-person? Will students primarily receive assessments on paper or using an online homework system?

- **Lectures with Labs.** Some courses are taught in large lecture halls with multiple smaller “lab” sections scheduled during the week. Will assessments be consistent across all the sections of the lab and how is that coordinated?
- **Access to technology.** How does access to technology in the classroom inform the assessments you give? Will students have clickers or personal devices in class so they can respond to in-class questions? Are there computers for every student or pair of students? What technology do students learn with, and is that technology to be used during the assessment?

Assessment in the Age of Advancing Technology (e.g., AI)

The release of ChatGPT and similar large language models surprised educators with their ability to simulate natural conversation and its potential impact on students’ assessment. While AI may have initially seemed like an existential crisis in education, it is part of a continuing trend of technological advancements (like the internet and calculators) that require educators to adapt.

Whether the relevant technology represents a once-in-a-generation leap or just the latest R package, the guiding principle for integration into the curriculum is unchanged: the learning objectives dictate the appropriate response. With respect to assessment, two questions that educators have always needed to consider are whether and how each new technology is used.

For example, in considering the first question, it is incumbent for instructors to convey to students appropriate and inappropriate use of technology specific to teaching, learning, and assessment. There are many ways this can happen, including inviting students to contribute to drafting a class policy in collaboration with the instructor. Relatedly, it can be useful to reflect on whether the technology is used as a ‘tool’ (more efficient return on invested effort of the student as they achieve some desired learning objective) or a ‘crutch’ (students rely on the technology too heavily which undermines their learning) as a litmus test for appropriate and inappropriate uses.

In answering the second question, instructors might consider how the use of the technology might enhance or broaden student learning. For example, an instructor might use AI to foreground students’ evaluative thinking and conceptual understanding, by providing students with a prompt relevant to a course learning objective and an authentic AI-generated response to material that they are then prompted to evaluate, critique, or improve. For example, students could ask an AI chatbot to respond to a prompt such as “what does the term ‘confidence’ mean when statisticians report a 95% confidence interval” or “what happens to the results of a t-test if there is an outlier in the data?” and then critique the response.

Lastly, educators should not expect to shoulder the responsibility to digest and integrate new technologies alone. Just as resources and guidance were available for educators in the advent of technology in years prior, there are already several resources available for dealing with artificial

intelligence. *Generative AI and the Future of Education* (2023) and the Cardona et al. (2023) and other authorities published reports almost immediately after ChatGPT was introduced to the public. Many universities also have resources and guidance available.

Additional Resources

- [Annotated bibliography](#)
- Examples
- Assessments

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Recommendation 10

Jo Hardin (chair), Allison Theobald, Suzy Thornton, Maria Tackett

Implement inclusive strategies that create learning environments where all students are valued.

Thank you for clicking on this recommendation! We know how overwhelming it can be to create a course that is inclusive of all students. Building an inclusive classroom is an iterative process which requires constant reflection on student needs, as well as our own. In the guideline below we have done our best to create “bite size” recommendations for a variety of dimensions of teaching, supporting you in navigating your inclusive teaching journey.

Introduction

Learning statistics equips students to take a well-informed and intelligent approach as they engage with the vast amounts of data and statistics in modern society (Ben-Zvi and Garfield 2008). Therefore, it is imperative that all students have an opportunity to succeed in their statistics and data science courses and to be “better prepared to grapple with the complexities of our technological society” (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine 2025, 17). Charles A. Dana Center (2021, 3) describes this as “a moral and a professional obligation to create the conditions necessary for every student to succeed.” Despite the obligation, students from groups historically marginalized in STEM are less likely to complete degrees in STEM disciplines, including statistics and data science, than their peers despite entering college with a comparable level of interest (Theobald et al. 2020). Students from historically marginalized groups are more likely to forgo further study in STEM disciplines due to experiencing an “unwelcoming atmosphere” (Olson and Riordan 2012) or having a lesser sense of belonging (e.g, Good et al. 2012; Strayhorn 2019). Society misses out on the knowledge and perspective historically marginalized students can offer when they leave the discipline. Given the complexity of challenges facing society, we need diverse perspectives to rise to the level of innovation required to solve them (Chaffee et al. 2025).

Students from historically marginalized groups may experience undo barriers that produce inequities in their opportunities to succeed in their studies. Unequal barriers can be mitigated

through an inclusive pedagogy that gives all students an equal opportunity to achieve success (Byra 2006; Moriña 2022). Inclusive pedagogy can increase students' sense of belonging, increase self-efficacy, and reduce disparities in academic performance (Valdez and Kelp 2023). Such efforts foster a sense of belonging, which has been shown to increase student engagement (Wilson et al. 2015), and students who are actively engaged have a stronger understanding of the course content and are thus better prepared to apply concepts in new contexts (Weiland and Williams 2024; National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine 2025). Students in classrooms that implement inclusive pedagogies also report higher self-efficacy (Valdez and Kelp 2023). Self-efficacy is a strong predictor of academic performance beyond students' ability, as students with high self-efficacy are more motivated to persevere when faced with obstacles (Zimmerman 2000; Rittmayer and Beier 2008; Sandrone 2022; Valdez and Kelp 2023). Additionally, inclusive pedagogies can increase classroom community, which can enhance students' sense that they are valued by the field, ultimately impacting the decisions students make as they choose an academic path and career (Valdez and Kelp 2023).

Definitions

To ground our discussion, we offer definitions of “inclusivity” and “valued.” Through understanding of different perspectives, we can hone our teaching in such a way to bring all students successfully into our classrooms.

Inclusivity

Inclusivity refers to the practice of creating an environment where all individuals, regardless of their backgrounds, identities, or abilities, feel welcomed, respected, valued, and supported. Inclusivity involves actively acknowledging and valuing the natural variability that exists across student experiences, working to ensure students have the resources and opportunities they need to be successful, and creating an environment where every student feels they can thrive.

Valued:

Being valued refers to the sense that other people regard us as important, the belief that other people depend on us, and the realization that other people are actively paying attention to us (Rosenberg and McCullough 1981). In an academic setting, being valued is often described as “feeling cared about, accepted, respected, and important to others” (Strayhorn 2019, 4). Being valued emphasizes the need for others to recognize you as an individual in a way that honors your sense of self.¹

¹In the literature, you may encounter references to “belonging” and “mattering” instead of “valuing.” While there are some important differences in how researchers define the ideas (see Ajjawi et al. 2023; Mann 2005; Reay et al. 2010; Thomas 2015; Yuval-Davis 2006), the GAISE committee decided to use the term “valued”

Implementation

There are countless ways in which an instructor can cultivate a learning environment where students are valued. For example, the course preparation stage is a great opportunity to get a jump start on inclusivity efforts, by considering possible accessibility needs as they relate to the design of the course. When preparing their course, an instructor can preemptively reflect upon whether there are course components that could present barriers to the full participation or benefit of any student, such as students with different visual and / or auditory abilities, students who don't have access to internet at home, or students who are nervous about speaking up in class. The course preparation stage is just one place where instructors can consider ways to foster a learning environment where every student is valued. Changes, however, permeate every interaction instructors have with students, both inside and outside the classroom. In the [table of practices](#), we go into greater depth on a variety of changes instructors can make which “seek to dismantle systemic barriers in academia that may prevent full participation” of all students (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine 2025, 229).

Regardless of the number of inclusive strategies an instructor uses in their course, it is always important to obtain feedback from students on their experiences in the course. Student surveys can (and should) happen before the end of the course, so the instructor has sufficient time to act on changes that could break down barriers affecting certain students. We agree with (Dalzell et al. 2025) that there “is value in communicating the intentionality of our course design to our students and inviting them to share if the structure works for them”. Consistent, reciprocal communication lies at the heart of any approach, conveying to students that their experiences matter and reiterating that their instructor values their perspective.

Conclusion

We are confident that if you have considered the GAISE guidelines, you are an instructor who cares deeply about the quality of your course and the success of your students. Although it can seem overwhelming to consider the many dimensions of inclusive teaching, we must not let the perfect be the enemy of the good. In addition to the resources available in the [table of practices](#) that we provide, the internet is full of resources with tips and suggestions for all possible combinations of courses [large / medium / small], [online / in-person], [introductory / intermediate / advanced] with [traditional / non-traditional] students. Each step toward creating an inclusive learning environment which values learners, even steps that seem small, is beneficial and the accumulation of efforts over time will move the needle toward a more diverse and statistically literate population.

to represent the overarching idea of students feeling that they are valued by others.

Additional Resources

- [Table of practices](#)
- Annotated bibliography
- Examples
- Assessments

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Assessment

Assessment in Statistics and Data Science Education

Under Development

This section is currently under development. We are working to provide examples

- Formative and summative assessment strategies
- Authentic assessment approaches using real data
- Technology-enhanced assessment methods
- Inclusive assessment practices
- Assessment of statistical reasoning and communication skills
- Portfolio and project-based evaluation
- Standards and rubrics for different learning outcomes

Check back soon for detailed content, or visit our [\[Recommendations\]\(recommendations.qmd\)](#) page for current assessment-related guidance in Recommendation 9.

Coming Soon

Recommendation 10: Changes to Curricular & Pedagogical Practices

Changes for restructuring a classroom to be more inclusive of a diverse set of learners have multiple levels. As such, we have divided practices into different “orders” of change similar to the [National Academies of Sciences \(NASEM\)](#) (2025, 229), where each order is differentiated by the extent to the changes seek to dismantle systemic barriers in academia that may prevent full participation.

Within these “orders,” we have outlined changes in four dimensions—access, achievement, power, and identity. These dimensions are based on Dr. Rochelle Gutiérrez’s [article on framing equity](#) (2009).

- **Access** refers to the resources (content, human, environmental, etc.) available to students.
 - The access dimension reflects the idea that “students are affected by their ‘opportunity to learn’” (p. 5).
- **Achievement** refers to visible student outcomes.
 - The achievement dimension reflects the “serious economic and social consequences” (p. 5) for not doing well in a math-based field.
- **Identity** refers to the lived experiences of all involved in teaching and learning. The identity dimension:
 - acknowledges how students are racialized (Martin 2007), gendered (Langer-Osuna 2011), and classed (Walkerdine 1988),
 - considers whether “students have opportunities to draw upon their cultural and linguistic resources” (p. 5), and
 - pays attention to “whose perspectives and practices are ‘socially valorized’” (Abreu 2007).
- **Power** refers to the agency of all involved in the teaching and learning process. Power can be measured by:
 - a student’s “voice in the classroom dimension (e.g., who gets to talk, who decides the curriculum)” (Adler 1998; Zevenbergen 2000),

- opportunities for students to use statistics as an “analytic tool to critique society” (Gutiérrez 2009), and
- alternative notions of knowledge (D’Ambrosio 2006).

Gutiérrez situates these dimensions in terms of “dominant” and “critical” mathematics, ideas which complement the “orders” of organizational changes outlined by the NASEM (2025). Dominant mathematics is comprised of the access and achievement dimensions, which prepare students to participate economically in society and measure how well students can “play the game” of mathematics. These ideas are reflected in the first and second order changes outlined by NASEM (2025), which focus on changes that work within the confines of “typical” academic structures and do not seek to dismantle the structures themselves.

The identity and power dimensions comprise critical mathematics, which “acknowledges the positioning of students as members of society rife with issues of power and domination” (Gutiérrez 2007). The ideas of critical mathematics are seen in the third order changes, which expose and challenge the “structures and cultures that maintain inequity” (2025, 231).

First Order Changes

Changes at this level focus primarily on issues related to “access”—“the resources that students have available to them to participate in [statistics]” (Gutiérrez 2009). These first order changes focus on students’ access to environments which support their learning, both inside and outside the classroom.

How do students access the materials required for their course?

- What are the costs associated with the course? How are they prohibitive for students?
 - [Open-access \(free\) materials for mathematics and statistics](#)
- How are you presenting the course material(s)? How are the methods prohibitive for students with visual and auditory limitations?
 - *Evaluating Pedagogical Choices with an Inclusive Approach* (Dalzell 2024)
 - *Framework for Accessible and Inclusive Teaching Materials for Statistics and Data Science Courses* (Dogucu 2023)

How do students access their teachers?

- Reframing “office hours” to describe what their purpose is (“student hours”) or the outcome you hope (“happy hours”).
 - Telling students that office hours *are* student hours, that they don’t have to go alone, and that they can ask questions beyond the course material (Peter Felten and Tapia 2023).

- Rebranding office hours so they sound like something students *want* to attend (Benaduce and Brinn 2024).
- Does the language you use alienate certain groups of students?
 - [Using welcoming rather than punitive language in your syllabus](#)
 - Using inclusive, people-first and identity-first language (American Psychological Association 2020; National Institute of Standards and Technology 2021)
 - Recognize that students will feel most comfortable in a classroom where they feel respected—use students’ preferred names and pronouns.
 - * Also recognize the vulnerability of students whose name and / or pronouns could make them susceptible to prejudice (Rehnberg and Theobald 2024).
 - Using audio recordings that help you [learn how to pronounce students’ names](#).
 - Use terms for groups of people that are not gendered (e.g., “folks” or “people” rather than “guys”; “first-year students” rather than “freshmen”).
- “Explicitly name and model the importance of seeking out resources and academic help” (Dewsbury 2020).
 - Suggestions on how to do this: <https://cndls.georgetown.edu/resources/ip-toolkit/mentorship/>

Was the curriculum designed with a student-focused approach?

- “Employ evidence-based pedagogies that actively engage students in the learning process.” (See [Recommendation 8](#) for more detail)
- Universal design provides a framework for creating learning environments where *every* learner can participate in meaningful, challenging learning opportunities (CAST 2024).
 - **Engagement** – learners differ substantially in what motivates and engages them in their learning.
 - **Representation** – learners differ in the ways they perceive and make meaning of information.
 - **Action & Expression** – learners differ in how they navigate a learning environment, their approach to the learning process, and how they express what they know.

What is the infrastructure for learning outside of class?

- Do students need internet to complete their work or access the class resources?
 - Be aware that not every student has access to home internet, which affects the work they are able to accomplish once they leave campus, their access to discussion boards for asking questions and seeing other students’ responses, receiving updates on assignment deadlines and corrections.

- What are the costs associated with the software you are using? What type of computer do students need to have to access this software? (See [Recommendation 6](#) for more detail.)
- What are the time expectations for working outside of class? Are the expectations prohibitive for students who work or have care giving responsibilities?
 - Be aware that the guidelines of 2-3 hours per week spent studying *outside* of class for every credit hour may be intractable for students who work or have care giving responsibilities.
 - Consider integrating “work sessions” inside the classroom, reducing the amount of work outside of class **and** giving students access to you (the instructor) while they work (Hogan and Sathy 2022).

Second Order Changes

This second level of changes focus on relationships, classroom practices, and norms. These changes consider students’ achievement—“tangible results for students at all levels” (Gutiérrez 2009, 5). Grades are the primary mechanism by which we quantify and communicate with students about their achievement. Yet, grades also affect “the future courses students might take, the major(s) they might pursue, graduation timelines, job prospects, eligibility for academic awards and scholarships, and more” (Grinde et al. 2024). So, care should be taken to create a more equitable and inclusive assessment system, to reduce the negative downstream consequences for students

How do students demonstrate what they’ve learned?

- How are students expected to “show” you what they learned?
 - Providing multiple options for students to demonstrate their learning (Dalzell et al. 2025; Davidson 2024; Theobald 2021; Reinhart et al. 2022)
 - “Use a variety of formative and summative assessments to improve teaching and learning.” (See [Recommendation 9](#) for more detail.)
- How does your assessment system help students learn and grow from their mistakes? Does your assessment system penalize students for the speed at which they learn?
 - [Reattempts without penalty](#) (Clark and Talbert 2023)
 - [Questions \(and Answers\) for Incorporating Nontraditional Grading in Your Statistics Courses](#) (Brenna Curley and Reyes 2024)
 - [Inclusive Pedagogy Toolkit - Assessment](#)
- How much are students’ grades based on their behaviors instead of their learning? (Feldman 2023, grading-for-growth)
 - Classroom participation
 - * [Ways to elicit participation without grading it](#)

- * [Engagement credits](#)
 - Late deductions
 - * [Real world approach to deadlines](#)
- How much of students' grades are based on a hidden curriculum? (Hogan and Sathy 2022)
 - [Mastering the Hidden Curriculum](#) (course for students)
 - [Revealing the hidden curriculum](#) (for teachers)

How does your assessment system impact your relationship with students?

- How you communicate with students about their learning / feedback.
 - [Provide marks that indicate progress](#) (Clark and Talbert 2023)
 - [Providing specific, actionable feedback](#) (Clark and Talbert 2023)
 - [Pairing grades with feedback is less effective than just giving feedback](#) (Butler and Nisan 1986)
 - [Providing feedback \(both positive and negative\) is mentoring!](#)
- How do you respond to (dis)ability related needs? (Edwards et al. 2022)
 - Recognize that the landscape of classroom accommodations is constantly changing. Students today might have a very different experience from what university was like for you, and that's okay! (Zhang et al. 2010)
 - How do you respond to / inform students that you've received notice of their needs from the university (e.g. DRC office)?
 - * Review your university's guidelines on how you communicate with students regarding their accommodations **and** how students are expected to communicate with you.
 - * Tell students your expectations regarding how they communicate with you about their accommodations. For example, how should students tell you they need a deadline extension? How should they tell you they need to miss class?
 - How do students communicate to you if they have specific needs that have not been recognized by the university's disability office?
 - * Consider the time and resources needed for students to obtain university-sanctioned accommodations, and think about ways to integrate accommodations for *every* student. For example, giving every student 120-minutes to complete a 60-minute exam.

How do students participate in class?

- Consider developing classroom discussion guidelines. These can and should be developed in collaboration with students!
 - [Sample discussion guidelines from University of Denver](#)

- [Guidelines for inclusive discussions](#)
- Consider how you will respond to [conflict in your classroom](#)
- “Create a culture of mentoring with your students and in your classes” (Dewsbury 2020).
 - Resources for how to do this: <https://cndls.georgetown.edu/resources/ip-toolkit/mentorship/>

Third Order Changes

In their report NASEM states that “any effort to make STEM more diverse, inclusive, and equitable demands the deepest and most difficult kind of change: third order change” (2025, 231). Changes at this level interrogate underlying models, structures, and cultures which maintain inequity. We believe these third order changes are reflected in the “critical axis” Gutiérrez outlines, where “identity can be seen as a precursor to power, ensures that students’ frames of reference and resources are acknowledged in ways that help build critical citizens so that they may change the game” (2009, 6).

Identity

- Who is represented in your curriculum?
 - [CURV \(connecting, uplifting, and recognizing voices\)](#) is a database used to introduce students to scholars who have been historically underrepresented in statistics and data science, combating homogeneity of representation in the statistics curriculum.
 - Include a wide range of perspectives, experiences, and backgrounds in your course materials, and also voice a wide range of perspectives *yourself* (Dewsbury 2020).
 - How are you acknowledging and discussing the intertwined history of Statistics and eugenics? (Dewsbury 2020; Kennedy-Shaffer 2024)
- What type of data are you using in your course? Whose perspectives are valued by those data?
 - Weiland & Williams (2024) describe the importance of instructors drawing on “culturally relevant data,” echoing the continued call for culturally relevant and responsive teaching (Gay 2018, 2002; Ladson-Billings 1995).
 - * [The Violence Project](#)
 - * [The Eviction Lab](#)
 - * [The Generations Study](#)
 - Recognizing how gender is represented in the data you use and how that affects the experiences of LGBTQ+ students in your classroom (Miller and Hardin 2019; Rehnberg and Theobald 2024).

- “Data are not neutral or objective. They are the products of unequal social relations, and this context is essential for conducting accurate, ethical analysis” (D’Ignazio and Klein 2020). Regardless of the data you use in class, time should be spent discussing the social, cultural, historical, and institutional context of the data (Dalzell et al. 2025).
- How do you lift up the voices of individuals from historically underrepresented groups?
 - Consider using [the equip app](#) (Reinholz and Shah 2018) to track how *you* (the instructor) respond to the ideas students pose.
 - “Treat your students as scholars” (Dewsbury 2020).
 - * Resources on how to do this: <https://cndls.georgetown.edu/resources/ip-toolkit/mentorship/>
 - Appreciate that not every student feels comfortable sharing for a variety of reasons, among which are the societal expectations and biases to which they are subject.
 - * Consider setting expectations for an *accountable space*¹, where students are responsible for their words, actions, and intentions. These expectations make **everyone** responsible for behaving equitably and inclusively.
 - * Look into resources for setting the stage for and managing classroom discourse: <https://cndls.georgetown.edu/resources/inquiry-discourse-toolkit/>
- Reflect on the ways *your* identity, experiences, and culture influence your own teaching.
 - “Consider how your own social identities are relevant to the power dynamics at play” (Dewsbury 2020).
 - * Suggestions on how to do this: <https://cndls.georgetown.edu/resources/ip-toolkit/power/#consider-how-your-own-social-identities-are-relevant-to-the-power-dynamics-at-play>
 - “Train to be a better mentor to **all** your students” (Dewsbury 2020).
 - * Suggestions on how to do this: <https://cndls.georgetown.edu/resources/ip-toolkit/mentorship/>

Power

- Recognizing the cultural wealth students of color bring to the classroom (Yosso 2005) that often go unacknowledged and unrecognized.
 - “Allow students leadership roles during class sessions; give them opportunities to share their expertise” (Dewsbury 2020).

¹We are specifically focusing on “accountable” spaces instead of “safe” or “brave” spaces, as the language used to describe these spaces is evasive to the daily bravery marginalized communities “need to display everywhere, to navigate everyday and common biases, discrimination, and microaggressions, in workplaces and society” (Ahenkorah 2020).

- * Resources on how to do this: <https://cndls.georgetown.edu/resources/ip-toolkit/power/#consider-how-your-own-social-identities-are-relevant-to-the-power-dynamics-at-play>
 - Understanding and valuing why students from working class families might not ask for help or come to your office (student) hours (Jack 2019).
- Are you giving students opportunities to use statistics as an analytic tool for issues important to them?
 - Are there ways for you to give students the opportunity to work with data on issues that are important to them?
- How does your curriculum put power in students’ hands?
 - Are there ways for you to give students the opportunity to decide what topic(s) are included in the course?
 - * Suggestions on how to do this: <https://cndls.georgetown.edu/resources/ip-toolkit/power/#when-feasible-involve-students-directly-in-shaping-your-syllabus-and-pedagogical-choices>
- How does your assessment system put power in students’ hands?
 - Are there ways for you to give students the opportunities to decide how they want to be assessed? (Myint 2023)

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